

Interpolation Accuracy Evaluation for 3D Radio Environment Maps Construction

Antoni Ivanov^{*,†,‡}, Krasimir Tonchev[†], Vladimir Poulkov^{†,‡}, Agata Manolova[†], Atanas Vlahov^{‡,†}

[†] Faculty of Telecommunications, Technical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

[‡] Research and Development and Innovation Consortium, Sofia Bulgaria

Email: astivanov@tu-sofia.bg^{*}, k_tonchev@tu-sofia.bg, vkp@tu-sofia.bg, amanolova@tu-sofia.bg, ici-lab@sofiatech.bg

Abstract—The characterization of the wireless spectrum in modern and future communications has been established as an important field of research, particularly in view of the increasing densification of terrestrial and aerial network nodes. Radio Environment Maps (REMs) have been prominently utilized for volumetric spectrum occupancy analysis and the design of algorithms for resource allocation but their construction relies on interpolation methods due to the limited availability of measurements. This paper evaluates four such estimators for two datasets collected in real-world environments in three-dimensional (3D) space - indoor through an automated measuring tool, and outdoor through a UAV-based sensor. The process of calibration of the interpolation methods is described, and their performance is assessed, reaching a minimum error of -7 dB. The influence of the distance between the measurement points and the estimated ones, on the accuracy, is analyzed. The findings in this work facilitate the further analysis in 3D signal propagation and REM prediction.

Keywords—Interpolation, Kriging, radio environment maps, unmanned aerial vehicles, volumetric measurements

I. INTRODUCTION

With the development of integrated aerial and terrestrial heterogeneous networks toward Sixth Generation (6G) use cases and applications, radio spectrum characterization and prediction has been established as an important field in telecommunications research [1], [2], [3], [4]. Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based communications provide services such as aerial base stations and backhaul for cellular users, key performance indicators analysis for network planning, delivery of goods, relaying between space and terrestrial nodes, and emergency network coverage, while indoor networks become increasingly dense and throughput-intensive. Thus, the complex propagation environment between densely deployed mobile user terminals, vehicular-based, and aerial communication nodes motivate the need for adaptive, computationally light and accurate algorithms for spectrum utilization and resource allocation [5], [2], [6]. One of the main enablers for these, is the REM which has recently been widely explored in cellular communications and cognitive radio (CR) literature in terms of

its construction from very limited measurements gathered by stationary, mobile terrestrial, and UAV-based sensors, as well as due to its capabilities for spectrum assessment (such as network coverage mapping through real-world received signal measurement collection) [6], [7], [8], [9]. This research topic is usually studied in terms of the following three aspects - the dimensionality of physical space in which the spectrum is characterized (two-dimensional, 2D, or three-dimensional, 3D), the method of interpolation to characterize the said space (which uses the measured signal power at measured points of space, to estimate the power at the unknown ones), and the radio environment's characteristics (indoor, outdoor terrestrial, or outdoor aerial) [8], [10]. Most of the existing works focus on simulating 2D and 3D measurements via ray tracing (RT) or statistical path loss models, produced by a stationary transmitter and collected by mobile terrestrial or aerial sensors [11], [12], [13], [14]. There are, however, some practical implementations, most of which considering REMs in 2D space (i.e. the sensor collects the measurements from a number of points on the same altitude, that form a plane) to characterize a cellular network's coverage [15], [16], while some limited work has been done on 3D spectrum characterization in the case of real-world UAV sources, with the radio frequency (RF) data collected by an aerial sensor (which is a more complicated endeavor due to the UAV's fast movement in 3D space and the change in the channel characteristics with altitude) [9]. The work in this research field advances the development of UAV-empowered communications enabled by volumetric spectrum sensing, spectrum patrolling, Wi-Fi/cellular networks coexistence, spectrum occupancy prediction and increased spectrum utilization in not just time and frequency but 3D space also [1], [3], [17].

This paper uses RF measurements collected in 3D real-time environments for the fine-tuning of the essential parameters of some of the most effective interpolation methods (nearest neighbor, linear, inverse distance weighting, and Kriging [7], [8], [11]) for REM construction, to assess their performance. Two scenarios in 2.4 GHz license-free bands are considered - indoor environment with dense deployment of stationary software defined radio (SDR) signal sources, and an outdoor scenario with UAVs communicating with their ground-based remote controllers (RCs). For the former, the measurements are collected by an SDR moved by a mechanical automated

* Corresponding author - Antoni Ivanov.

This research was supported by the EU Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange Programme "Research Collaboration and Mobility for Beyond 5G Future Wireless Networks (RECOM-BINE)" under grant agreement no. 872857 and the "Intelligent Communication Infrastructure Laboratory" at Sofia Tech Park, Sofia, Bulgaria.

positioning system (APS) at a number of locations on four different heights within the volume of the room [18]. In the latter scenario, the RF sensor is implemented via an SDR mounted on a separate UAV that follows a predetermined route to measure the received signal level within the band which the other UAVs communicate on, again covering a number of locations on four different altitudes [9]. By considering the measured points on all levels together, the interpolation accuracy for data in 3D space is determined. The contribution of this paper is summarized as follows:

- An evaluation of prominent interpolation methods for volumetric RF data gathered in real-world indoor and UAV-based scenarios, which is based on the calibration of their crucial parameters for improved accuracy toward REM construction in the considered volume. For both datasets which are comprised of the mean received signal values of all measurement points in 3D spatial coordinates, the interpolation is evaluated according to the amount of training data. Normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) of -2.8 and -7 dB has been achieved for the indoor and UAV-based scenarios, respectively. The influence of the distance between the measurement points and the estimated ones, on the accuracy, is analyzed. This investigation facilitates the further analysis of the spatial dynamics of the received signals' propagation in the two separate environments.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II. describes the two experimental setups for which the RF data is gathered, as well as the manner in which it is processed. Then, the methodology for calibrating the considered interpolation methods, and the estimation error results they yield, are analyzed in Section III. The conclusion to this work together with directions for further research are described in Section IV.

II. SUMMARY ON EXPERIMENTS AND RF DATA PROCESSING

A. APS Indoor 3D RF Measurements Scenario and Processing

The indoor experimental setup is implemented in a large laboratory that allows for the deployment of the APS and its robotic Automatic Positioning Tool (APT), controlled by a host computer (Fig. 1a). Hereby, only the most important details of the experimental setup will be described, while the complete explanation may be found in the previous work [18]. The APT can operate in 3D within a volume of dimensions of $[6 \times 2 \times 0.75]$ m, and for this experiment, it follows a pre-programmed route (shown in Fig. 1b) along the ordinate and abscissa axes for four levels of elevation - 0, 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 m above the surface of the table placed below the APT. On each elevation level, the APT moves along the same set of locations (denoted by an \times in Fig.1b) with a step of 0.8 m in the x -coordinate and 0.2 m in the y -coordinate. At each point, the SDR (Analog Devices PlutoSDR [19]) mounted on the APT, performs a single measurement while the APT remains stationary before it moves to the next point.

(a) APS - APT with mounted SDR and host computer in yellow, SDR transmitters in red.

(b) Measurement path on a single height level.

Fig. 1: APS indoor experimental setup.

Once all points on the same level are covered, the APT is lifted to the next elevation. The recorded Wi-Fi signals are emitted from four densely deployed SDR transmitters in the APT's immediate vicinity. The collected RF data is processed by dividing the measurement samples for each location into batches, and taking the mean among the highest signal levels for each batch (this filtering is done by adaptively changing the decision threshold value according to the procedure described in [18]). Thus, this mean value will describe the received signal level at each particular location in space.

B. UAV-based 3D RF Measurements Scenario and Processing

The experimental setup of UAV-based communications (Fig. 2a) is implemented in a large outdoor area of an aerial model flight club using three "sensed UAVs" - DJI Matrice 600 Pro, Inspire 2, and Mavic 2 Enterprise Dual, which exchange information with their ground-based RCs, and a separate "sensor UAV" (Freefly ALTA X), which measures the said signals through its on-board SDR, Nuand BladeRF 2.0 micro [20]. Again, only the basic details are given in this paper, while the comprehensive description of the experiment is provided in the previous work [9]. Similar to the APT in the indoor scenario, the sensor UAV covers a pre-determined trajectory that is comprised of 40 locations (shown in Fig. 2b) with equal distance between them, encompassing the , over each of which the UAV hovers for 5 seconds. The measurement points

outline an area with dimensions of 105×38 m for each of the four altitudes - 80, 90, 100, and 110 m above sea level. The sensed UAVs fly in a realistic constellation at altitudes 10 m above that of the sensor UAV at each altitude. The sensor UAV performs RF measurements on a single 20 MHz channel in the 2.4 GHz band, which is empirically found to be used by the sensed UAVs, for the whole duration of its flight at each altitude. The collected RF data is processed by taking

(a) Sensor UAV (in green) and sensed UAVs (in violet) in flight.

(b) Waypoint trajectory for the sensor UAV.

Fig. 2: UAV-based experimental setup.

the mean over the samples that correspond to the time period (5 seconds), during which the sensor UAV hovers over each of the 40 positions. These means can be estimated considering that the moment at which the sensor UAV has reached the altitude, and it takes about 4.7 seconds for the UAV to move between the positions. Their coordinates on the x and y axes are pre-determined (Fig. 2b) to form the flight trajectory.

III. INTERPOLATION METHODS CALIBRATION AND RESULTS ANALYSIS

A. Datasets Description

This Section details the study of the interpolation accuracy for four of the most prominent interpolation methods in current literature, as applied to the indoor and UAV-based measurements in 3D space. For both scenarios, the sensor SDR measures the spectrum at a central frequency F_C and a bandwidth of B Hz for a sampling frequency F_S , for the whole period T_F during which the measurement is performed. B , F_C and F_S are considered as constants, i.e. interpolation in frequency domain is not done. As a consequence, $N_S = T_F F_S$ measurement samples are obtained, which define the bandwidth at every measured location within the space \mathbb{A} that the experiment is performed in. Then, a subset $\mathcal{Z} = \{z_i\}_{i=1}^{N_P}$, $\mathcal{Z} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ of N_P samples is selected, such that

TABLE I: RF data and simulation parameters for the two scenarios (APS and UAV)

Parameter	Values		Parameter	Value
	APS	UAV		
B , MHz	5	20	Δ_T , %	[5; 5; 95]
F_C , MHz	2484	2427	N_z	[5; 5; 100]
N_P	35	40	ν	[0.05; 0.5; 9]
N_P'	140	160	α	[0.05; 0.5; 9]
N_H	4	4	N_I	100

$\mathcal{Z} \subset \mathbb{A}$, and z_i are the measurement points which are used for the interpolation task. These samples are comprised of the received power $\mathcal{P} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ at each point in \mathcal{Z} and form the subset $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathcal{P}(z_i)\}_{i=1}^{N_P}$. As illustrated in Fig. 1b and 2b, the measurement datasets for both scenarios are of size $N_P \times N_H$ where N_P and N_H denote the number of measurements per elevation level, and the number of levels, respectively. As stated in Section II, each measurement location is described by the mean signal power $\mathcal{P}(z_i)$ for the measurement duration T_F for a single point z_i , $i \in \mathcal{Z}$. The corresponding datasets of measurement points coordinates is of size $N_x \times N_y \times N_H$, where N_x and N_y denote the number of positions on the x and y axis, respectively, with $N_x = N_y$. The datasets of measured signal levels and their coordinates are divided into K batches which are used for the training and testing of the examined methods via the K -fold cross validation technique. The points in each fold are selected across all elevation levels and shuffled randomly. As the evaluated methods require the relationships between the measurement points to be relative to the 3D distance d between them, these datasets are converted into the size of $N_P' \times 3$, where the N_P' distances are obtained as $d = \sqrt{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2 + (y_{i+1} - y_i)^2 + (z_{i+1} - z_i)^2}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{Z}$, with \mathcal{Z} being the set of measurement points, and x , y and z representing the coordinates in the respective axes. The REM $\hat{\mathcal{R}}$ can be defined as a function $f(\cdot)$ that is obtained from the measured power \mathcal{P} at the points comprising the \mathcal{Z} subset, and it usually involves the interpolation of the powers $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ at a set $\mathcal{U} \notin \mathcal{Z}$ of points, so as to increase the REM's graphical resolution. The interpolation itself is in general, an estimation of \mathcal{P} at an unknown point u using the measurement points z_i , $i = \{1, \dots, N_P'\}$, through the use of an estimator described by the function $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$, as follows: $\hat{\mathcal{P}}(u_j) = \mathcal{F}[\mathcal{P}(z_i), z_i, u_j]$, $\forall z_i \in \mathcal{Z}$, $\forall u_j \in \mathcal{U}$. The solution of this function involves the estimation of its parameters denoted by $\boldsymbol{\eta} \in \mathbb{R}^M$. These parameters are obtained through the particular interpolation method.

The RF data and simulation parameters for the processing done to produce the following analysis, are summarized in Table I.

B. Interpolation Methods

The interpolation methods evaluated in this paper are the nearest neighbor, linear, inverse distance weighting, and ordinary Kriging, which will be briefly described below. Their

theoretical derivations will not be detailed for the sake of space, but they can be found in [7], [8], [11], [21].

The nearest neighbor interpolation presents the simplest estimator that increases the measurements' cardinality by repeating the nearest point's value, i.e. all points' estimation parameters η (weights) are equal. In other words, for each point u_j the power is equal to that of the closest point z_C with known power:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathcal{P}}(u_j) &= \mathcal{P}(z_C), \\ z_C &= \min\{\|z_i, u_j\|\}, \forall z_i \in \mathcal{Z}, \forall u_j \in \mathcal{U}.\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

As a particular case, $\mathcal{P}(u_j)$ can be obtained as a linear combination of the two neighboring samples, the linear interpolation is determined:

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}(u_j) = \mathcal{P}(z_{i+1}) + \frac{[\mathcal{P}(z_{i+1}) - \mathcal{P}(z_i)] S_c}{\mathcal{P}(z_i)}, \quad (2)$$

$$\forall z_i \in \mathcal{Z}, \forall u_j \in \mathcal{U},$$

$S_c \in \mathbb{R}$ being a scaling coefficient.

The IDW method considers different influence of the known measured points on the estimated ones, depending on the distance d between a predicted unknown point u_j and all observed points z_i :

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}(u_j) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_P} (d_i)^{-k} \mathcal{P}(z_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_P} (d_i)^{-k}}, \quad \forall z_i \in \mathcal{Z}, \forall u_j \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (3)$$

where k describes the weights' decline with distance.

The Kriging method is implemented in the following steps:

- Choose N_P points (out of the set \mathcal{Z}) that are closest to the unknown point u . These N_P points are fitted to an empirical variogram function $f(h)$ (such as Exponential, Matern or Spherical). The points' values are formed as a function of $\mathcal{P} = f(h)|_{i=1}^{N_P}$ by dividing the N_P points into subsets according to their distance from u .
- Then, for each subset, the variogram is described as:

$$\gamma_h = \frac{1}{2n(h)} \sum_{i=1}^{n(h)} (\mathcal{P}(z_i) - \mathcal{P}(z_i + h))^2, \quad (4)$$

where $n(h)$ is the number of point pairs of measured points that are separated by a distance h . Then, the variogram's form, as well as its parameters (*nugget*, *sill*, and *range*) are determined empirically from the resulting function. The nugget is the height of the variogram's jump at $h = 0$, the sill is the variogram's limit at $\gamma_h \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e. the variogram usually flattens after this value is reached), while the range is the distance h for which γ_h exceeds the sill for the first time.

- The Kriging weights η are computed via solving using the covariances between every two known points and between the estimated point and the observed points. These covariances are computed by equations determined by the variogram's form and depend on the distance h between the two points, the nugget, sill and range [21]. Finally, the estimated power $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ is found as $\hat{\mathcal{P}}(u_j) = \mathcal{P}\eta$.

The empirical determination of this method's parameters (variogram distribution, nugget, sill and range) will be described below.

C. Methodology for Estimation of the Kriging Empirical Variogram

Solving the Kriging interpolation depends to a great extent on the appropriate choice of the empirical variogram γ_h that most commonly assumes the following form [21]: $\gamma_h = \frac{1}{2n(h)} \sum_{i=1}^{n(h)} (\mathcal{P}(z_i) - \mathcal{P}(z_i + h))^2$, where $n(h)$ is the number of point pairs of measured points that are separated by a distance h . The variogram is implemented by drawing $n(h)$ points, from the input number of samples N_z at each iteration, which are within a particular distance h from the point $u_j \in \mathcal{U}$, the value of which is to be estimated from the rest. It has been a common practice in the REM interpolation literature to analyze the RMSE of the input RF data for several standard variogram models (most often these are the *Exponential*, *Matern* and *Spherical* distributions, which are considered in this work). The RMSE metric is normalized and defined as $NRMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_P} (\mathcal{P}_i - \hat{\mathcal{P}}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_P} \mathcal{P}_i^2}}$, where N_P is the number of points that are to be estimated. The normalization is done so as to represent the difference between the real value \mathcal{P} of the point, and its estimated value $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ regardless of the measured power's order of magnitude. If the difference between the real and estimated value is small, the NRMSE is < 0 (in dB), while if it is large in comparison to the real value's magnitude, the NRMSE will be $> 0dB$. The nugget, sill, and range are determined for each batch of N_z points that comprises the variogram. Determining the number of these points is thus a crucial aspect for each variogram model. Fig. 3 shows the results of the analysis for the achieved NRMSE by each variogram model for N_z in the range [5; 5; 100] while the amount Δ_T of training data is 95%. This is performed through Monte Carlo (MC) simulation of N_I iterations, for each of which, a separate set of indices of the input measurement data (that comprises a subset of \mathcal{Z} for each iteration) for all planes combined, is selected. At each iteration, K-fold cross validation is applied, i.e. 5% of all samples are selected at random, are shuffled, and taken as points the power of which is to be estimated, while the rest are shuffled as well and used as known data for the estimation. This process is repeated until all folds of samples have been considered, and the mean of their Kriging error standard deviation (STD) values is taken while the final STD is averaged over all iterations. The Kriging error STD measures the accuracy of the estimated $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$, and should be minimal [21]. K-fold cross validation is applied, i.e. 5% of all samples are selected at random, are shuffled, and taken as points the power of which is to be estimated, while the rest are shuffled as well and used as known data for the estimation. This process is repeated until all folds of samples have been considered, and the mean of their STD values is taken.

D. Estimation of the Empirical Variogram and Calibration of Interpolation Methods

In the case of the APS measurement data (Fig. 3a), it is notable, first of all, that applying the Matern model, yields the smallest STD by close to 1 dB to the alternatives for $N_z = 37$. The Spherical and Exponential models exhibit very similar results that are characterized by a nearly constant STD for $N_z \in [5; 37]$, which grows exponentially for $N_z \in (37; 60]$, and converges throughout the rest of the range. The 3D RF data gathered in indoor environment is characterized with little distance (0.2 m) between the points due to the limited space inside the vicinity. To explain the results in greater detail, the subsets of variogram points for $N_z \in [5; 37]$ and $N_z \in (37; 100]$, as well as their measured power values, are considered. The variances of the distances between every measurement point (that is included in the variogram) and the estimated one, and the corresponding powers of the measurement points for each N_z , are obtained. The mean of these variances is about 180 times smaller for $N_z \in [5; 37]$ than that of $N_z \in (37; 100]$, therefore in the latter interval, the measurement points included in the variogram, are significantly more distributed in 3D space. It should also be added that, the variances of the measured power's distribution is roughly the same for both intervals of N_z , which shows that the distribution of the variogram points in $N_z \in [5; 85]$ has decisive influence on the Kriging interpolation accuracy. This is due to the points' relative closeness (the mean distance between the variogram points and the estimated ones is < 4 m) to each other in this scenario, yet they are particular enough, in terms of their distance to the estimated points, and of their power values, as to decrease the STD. Increasing N_z further includes points that are less distinct in terms of their measured power, from each other, and their consideration can even lead to a higher error as exhibited for all three variogram models. When it comes to the alternative of RF data recorded for outdoor UAV-based communications scenario, the same evaluation exhibits similar features but with some deviations (Fig 3b). The tendency of the increase in Kriging error STD for a similar number of points ($N_z > 29$) is similarly prominent in this case which shows that including measurements in the variogram, that are at larger distance and/or higher altitude than the estimated point, also introduces a substantial degradation of the accuracy. This inclination is not surprising, considering that the dimensions ($105 \times 38 \times 30$ m) of the measurement space in this experiment are much greater in comparison to those ($6 \times 2 \times 0.75$ m) of the indoor scenario. Thus, the distance between the measurement points, is also significantly larger. In addition, the sensor UAV's movement is much more dynamic than that of the APS, which also leads to faster rate of change in the received signal's power [9]. For the whole interval of N_z , the STD differs very slightly for Matern and Exponential models, with the former performing better by about 0.5 dB. Additionally, the Spherical variogram yields about 3 dB worse results, than the alternatives. Similarly to the APS scenario, due to the higher

(a) APS indoor 3D RF measurements.

(b) UAV-based 3D RF measurements.

Fig. 3: Evaluation of the variogram models depending on the number of points $n(h)$ for the two scenarios.

dimensions of this one, increasing N_z is also unfavorable. To further understand this development, an analysis of the distances between the points selected for the variogram, and the estimated points is done. It is found that the mean of the variogram points' density for $n(h) \leq 29$, is 36 times higher (i.e. such points are considered in the variogram much more frequently), so they are of more importance for the estimation, than the points included for $n(h) > 29$. The variances of the points' distances for each N_z increase linearly until the threshold of 29 is reached. After this value, the variances exhibit an exponential growth (i.e. much more distant points are considered). With respect to the variogram points' power, however, the relationship is the opposite, i.e. the variances of the measured values in the two intervals of N_z are roughly equal. Therefore, it is the distance between the points that has the defining influence, regardless of the variogram's model.

As it has been established, the *Matern* variogram is most appropriate for both measurements scenarios. In addition to N_z , its performance depends on the smoothness parameter ν , which needs to be empirically determined. This is done via a very similar procedure to the above analysis for the choice of N_z , by setting Δ_T to 95% and N_z to the value that yields the minimum STD, i.e. 37 (APS scenario) and 29 (UAV scenario), while ν is changed from 0.05 to 9 with a step of 0.5. Thus, the optimal accuracy is achieved for $\nu = 0.05$ (APS scenario) and $\nu = 2.05$ (UAV scenario). Similarly, the coefficient α of

the IDW interpolation is determined from the interval $[0.05; 9]$ with a step of 0.5 for both scenarios, $\Delta = 95\%$. For the APS indoor scenario $\alpha = 1.05$, while for the UAV-based measurements $\alpha = 9.05$.

E. Comparison of Interpolation Methods Performance

Once the essential parameters of the interpolation methods are determined, their performance may be evaluated via simulations as follows. The four methods (IDW, linear, NN, and Kriging) are assessed for varying Δ_T in the interval $[5; 95]\%$ with step of 5% (Fig. 4). K-fold cross validation within a MC simulation, is applied for each Δ_T . For the APS indoor case (Fig. 4a), the following traits in the NRMSE distributions are observed. First of all, there is a notable decline in the error for the IDW estimator for $\Delta_T > 55\%$, while for the NN, the results have the opposite inclination. In the case of Kriging, there is an increase in the NRMSE for $\Delta_T \in (55; 70]\%$, after which interval, it declines steadily until it reaches the accuracy already achieved by the IDW method. As explained above, this environment is characterized by relatively small distances between the measurement points, compared to the alternative scenario. As Δ_T increases, there is a higher probability that the closest measurement points will be used for the interpolation, which is favorable for the IDW due to its weight decline coefficient being small, and only the nearest points are considered, until a convergence is reached. The Kriging estimator, despite of its higher computational complexity, performs slightly worse as it is not able to properly differentiate between the points' measured power within the dimensions of the scenario's measurement space because the information provided by the measurements does not change significantly as Δ_T increases, despite of the small smoothing parameter. Thus, it requires a higher density of the available measurements. As for the NN interpolation, an unusual increase of NRMSE is observed for $\Delta_T > 30\%$. It can be explained analogically, as the distance between the measurement points being too large for the closest neighboring points to necessarily result in a lower NRMSE as the variance of the measurement points' power has only negligible change with the increase of Δ_T . The lowest NRMSE is -2.8 dB (for IDW). Finally, the results for the linear interpolation are given in a separate subfigure as their order of magnitude is much higher than that of the rest. It is observed that the NRMSE changes inconsistently with Δ_T to the point that their distribution tends to be almost entirely sporadic, however, its variation is very small.

For the scenario for measurements of UAV-based communications (Fig 4b), the tendencies are notably different. The NRMSE of the linear method is higher than in the alternative scenario, which can be found in the much longer distance between the measurement points in 3D space in the UAV scenario. At the same time, the IDW and Kriging methods achieve significantly better results which are improved consistently with the increase of Δ_T . The Kriging method achieves a steady decline in the NRMSE, in a nearly exponential manner for $\Delta_T > 40\%$, and outperforms the IDW method for $\Delta_T > 85\%$.

(a) APS indoor 3D RF measurements.

(b) UAV-based 3D RF measurements.

Fig. 4: Evaluation of the interpolation methods depending on the percentage of training data Δ_T for the two scenarios.

For smaller Δ_T , however, the calibrated IDW has an advantage once again, but its coefficient α shows much steeper decline in the weights of the measurement points. In other words, due to the long distances among the points, and the high variance of the received signal at lower altitudes [9], only the closest ones have significant influence. As for the Kriging interpolation, it clearly exhibits the best accuracy by about 2 dB in comparison to the IDW for high Δ_T . The method is also much more rigorous to the signal level variations in 3D space with even less measurement points for its variogram, thus decreasing the computational complexity. Kriging is the most potent of the four interpolators, reaching NRMSE of -7 dB for REM estimation with limited RF data in the case of UAV-based communications. Even though, the precision in determining the measurement points' coordinates is lower (due to the UAV sensor not having a fixed position) than the indoor APS experiment, due to the sensor UAV's movement, Kriging (and to a lesser extent, the IDW estimator) is applicable to the interpolation problem.

The substantial difference in the results for these two scenarios despite the measurements for both being collected at equal distances from each other, show that the scale of the measurement area is an important consideration for the interpolation accuracy. Due to the much smaller distance between the points for the APS case, the path loss and scattering have significantly smaller influence and the received

signal strength is higher, than in the UAV-based scenario [9], [18]. This effect is observed because the distance to the transmitter for many of the measurement points, is only slightly larger than the wavelength. Then, in order for the signal propagation dynamics to be more accurately captured in the APS case, a smaller distance between the measurement points is necessary as the measured power variance will also be decreased. In contrast, the UAV-based measurements result in greater variance in the received signal level due to multipath and distance loss, which are appropriately modeled by the Kriging method to allow for an increased accuracy for a relatively low number of measurement points (that are nearest to the estimated ones).

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work presents an evaluation of four standard interpolation methods for REM construction, applied to two RF datasets collected from real-world experiments in an indoor environment via the APS robot, and outdoor UAV-based communications. The process of calibration for the Kriging and the IDW estimators is described and their results are analyzed together with those achieved by the linear and NN methods, for the two scenarios. In summary, it has been found that the calibrated Kriging (with Matern variogram model) and the IDW achieve the best accuracy, as the received signal variation with distance in 3D space can be compensated to a large extent through appropriate choice of the interpolation parameters. Nevertheless, these variations in the APS case necessitate shorter distance between the measurement points. This study will be extended to include further detail into the relationship between the interpolation of measurements on a single altitude and in 3D space, application of deep learning and graph neural networks in regions of interest-driven measurement collection for REM estimation, and adaptive REM prediction coupled with spectrum sensing for CR applications in 3D environments. The research will give further insight into the spectrum utilization and throughput improvement of UAV-to-UAV communications and coexisting indoor ultra-dense networks in both industrial prototyping and scientific study.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Mishra and E. Natalizio, "A survey on cellular-connected uavs: Design challenges, enabling 5g/b5g innovations, and experimental advancements," *Computer Networks*, vol. 182, p. 107451, 2020.
- [2] C.-X. Wang, X. You, X. Gao, X. Zhu, Z. Li, C. Zhang, H. Wang, Y. Huang, Y. Chen, H. Haas *et al.*, "On the road to 6g: Visions, requirements, key technologies and testbeds," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 2023.
- [3] W. Saad, M. Bennis, and M. Chen, "A vision of 6g wireless systems: Applications, trends, technologies, and open research problems," *IEEE network*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 134–142, 2019.
- [4] T. Cooklev, V. Poulkov, D. Bennett, and K. Tonchev, "Enabling rf data analytics services and applications via cloudification," *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, vol. 33, no. 5-6, pp. 44–55, 2018.
- [5] M. Mozaffari, W. Saad, M. Bennis, Y.-H. Nam, and M. Debbah, "A tutorial on uavs for wireless networks: Applications, challenges, and open problems," *IEEE communications surveys & tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 2334–2360, 2019.
- [6] H. B. Yilmaz, T. Tugcu, F. Alagöz, and S. Bayhan, "Radio environment map as enabler for practical cognitive radio networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 51, no. 12, pp. 162–169, 2013.
- [7] P. Kaniewski, J. Romanik, E. Golan, and K. Zubeł, "Spectrum awareness for cognitive radios supported by radio environment maps: Zonal approach," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 7, p. 2910, 2021.
- [8] Y. S. Reddy, A. Kumar, O. J. Pandey, and L. R. Cenkeramaddi, "Spectrum cartography techniques, challenges, opportunities, and applications: A survey," *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, vol. 79, p. 101511, 2022.
- [9] A. Ivanov, B. Muhammad, K. Tonchev, A. Mihovska, and V. Poulkov, "Uav-based volumetric measurements toward radio environment map construction and analysis," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 24, p. 9705, 2022.
- [10] M. Höyhtyä, A. Mämmelä, M. Eskola, M. Matinmikko, J. Kalliovaara, J. Ojanieni, J. Suutala, R. Ekman, R. Bacchus, and D. Roberson, "Spectrum occupancy measurements: A survey and use of interference maps," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 2386–2414, 2016.
- [11] P. Maiti and D. Mitra, "Ordinary kriging interpolation for indoor 3d rem," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, pp. 1–15, 2022.
- [12] R. Shrestha, D. Romero, and S. P. Chepuri, "Spectrum surveying: Active radio map estimation with autonomous uavs," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.04125*, 2022.
- [13] Q. Wu, F. Shen, Z. Wang, and G. Ding, "3d spectrum mapping based on roi-driven uav deployment," *IEEE Network*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 24–31, 2020.
- [14] X. Du, Q. Zhu, G. Ding, J. Li, Q. Wu, T. Lan, Z. Lin, W. Zhong, and L. Han, "Uav-assisted three-dimensional spectrum mapping driven by spectrum data and channel model," *Symmetry*, vol. 13, no. 12, p. 2308, 2021.
- [15] V. Platzgunner, V. Raida, G. Krainz, P. Svoboda, M. Lerch, and M. Rupp, "Uav-based coverage measurement method for 5g," in *2019 IEEE 90th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2019-Fall)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [16] V. Semkin, S. Kang, J. Haarla, W. Xia, I. Huhtinen, G. Geraci, A. Lozano, G. Lojanno, M. Mezzavilla, and S. Rangan, "Lightweight uav-based measurement system for air-to-ground channels at 28 ghz," in *2021 IEEE 32nd Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 848–853.
- [17] M. A. Khan, R. Hamila, M. S. Kiranyaz, and M. Gabbouj, "A novel uav-aided network architecture using wi-fi direct," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 67 305–67 318, 2019.
- [18] A. Ivanov, V. Stoyanov, R. Petkova, K. Tonchev, A. Manolova, and V. Poulkov, "Interference and spatial throughput characterization through practical 3d mapping in dense indoor iot scenarios," in *2020 23rd International Symposium on Wireless Personal Multimedia Communications (WPMC)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [19] Analog Devices, Inc. ADALM-PLUTO — Software-Defined Radio Active Learning Module. [Online]. Available: <https://www.analog.com/en/design-center/evaluation-hardware-and-software/evaluation-boards-kits/adalm-pluto.html>
- [20] Nuand. bladeRF 2.0 micro. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nuand.com/bladerf-2-0-micro/>
- [21] J. C. Davis and R. J. Sampson, *Statistics and data analysis in geology*. Wiley New York, 1986, vol. 646.